

4Q2 (4QGen-b) frag. 1 ii + frag. 4

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1 Identifying 4Q2 frag. 4

The editor of 4Q2, James Davila, observed about 4Q2 frag. 4 that “the leather quality, colour, and script of this fragment are the same as those of the other fragments of 4QGen^b.”¹ However, due to the darkening of the leather, he could not make good sense of the text of this fragment, which, in his reading, “does not seem to be from Genesis.”

4Q2 frag. 4 on PAM 43.004; photographer Najib Anton Albina
screenshot from <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-284244>

Only on the final photograph of 4Q2 in the PAM series, PAM 43.004, the fragment had been added to the other 4Q2 fragments. Though the print from which the editor had to work did not enable him to identify the letters correctly, the digital image of PAM 43.004 of the Leon Levy Dead Sea Scrolls Digital Library of the IAA²—as well as the recent new IAA photograph³—does enable one to decipher the few traces on the fragment, and connect them to the text of Gen 3:22-24.

ישל]ח ידו ולקח גם מעץ החיים ואכל וחי לעלם וישלחהו יהוה אלהים מגן]	1
עדן לעב]ד את האדמה אשר לקח משם ויגרש את האדם וישכן מקדם]	2
לגן ע]דן	3

¹James R. Davila, “2. 4QGen^b,” in *Qumran Cave 4.VII: Genesis to Numbers*, ed. Eugene Ulrich et al., DJD 12 (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1994), 31-38 at 31.

²<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-284244>.

³Not uploaded on the Leon Levy Dead Sea Scrolls Digital Library, but available from the Israel Antiquities Authority (Plate 215 frag. 6)

Crucial for the identification is the correct reading of the first words of lines 2 and 3, which the editor read differently due to damages to the surface of the scroll. The textual identification of the fragment is supported by the plausible physical join of frag. 4 to the left side of frag. 1 ii.

4Q2 frags. 1 ii (right) and frag. 4 (most left piece); joined with Gimp
Images Israel Antiquities Authority Plate 215 frags. 4 left and 6; photographer Shai Halevi

On the basis of this join one can assign 4Q2 frags. 1, 2 and 4 to three consecutive columns of 40/41 lines per column:

col.	reconstructed content	fragments	preserved content	preserved lines	letters/spaces per line (avg.)
I	Gen 1:1-30/31	frags. 1 i, 2	Gen 1:1-25 (frag. 1 i) Gen 1:25-28 (frag. 2)	1-30 (frag. 1 i) 31-35 (frag. 2)	55
II	Gen 1:30/31-3:7/8	frag. 1 ii	Gen 2:14-29 (frag. 1 ii)	17-23 (frag. 1 ii)	54
III	Gen 3:7/8-4:15(?)	frag. 4	Gen 3:22-24 (frag. 4)	18-20 (frag. 4)	59

2 **Where to place 4Q2 frag. 3 in the scroll?**

One would expect 4Q2 frag. 3 i, which has text from Gen 4:2-11, to derive from col. III, two or three lines beneath frag. 4. However, the average number of letter/spaces of frag. 3 i is only 48, considerably lower than the 59 of frag. 4 lines 1-2, and also much lower than would be needed for reconstruction of the top 17 lines of col. III. Admittedly, one should be cautious with calculations of lines and columns based on reconstructions of large sections of the text. Nonetheless, the difference is striking, and cannot easily be explained from features known from other scrolls.

Either the scribe wrote shorter lines in this part of the column preserved in frag. 3. A possible reason could be flaw in the writing surface. Or the scribe started chapter 4 on a new column, thus leaving the bottom half of col. III unwritten, a feature not attested in any other scroll. We do not have enough evidence to draw any firm conclusions.